

Perspectives on sugar consumption expressed on social media by French-speaking and Danish-speaking parents

Abstract

Introduction: Meanings and practices attributed to sugar emerged as important barriers to healthy eating in an earlier study with French and Danish parents. Considering the impact of excessive sugar intake on human health and childhood obesity, this study focuses on gaining further understanding of connotations, perceptions and attitudes related to sugar among parents. **Methods:** A thematic analysis of sugar-related posts and comments on blogs and Facebook pages was performed, and in-depth interviews with experts (one in each country) were conducted. Data were set in a Social Judgment Theory analytical framework. **Results:** Sugar consumption appears as a two-sided experience, being at times dangerous, sinful and addictive, but also comforting and delightful. This “sugar dilemma” unfolded aspects between asceticism and hedonism, state governance and personal responsibility. Three main behavioral strategies on how parents deal with these ambivalences emerged: i) restriction, ii) moderation, and iii) liberation. Restriction was more noticeable in France, whereas liberation was more pronounced in Denmark. In both countries, the ones who defended the respective opposite positions (restriction or liberation) were targets of judgmental moral tones. The three behavioral strategies corresponded to the main attitudes demonstrated in reaction to anti-sugar messages, which align to the Social Judgment Theory constructs: acceptance, non-commitment and rejection. **Conclusions:** Findings shed light on dietary, behavioral and social challenges faced by parents and highlight the importance of a diversified approach to tackle sugar consumption among families - an approach that considers

individuals' attitudes, social context and value systems. Furthermore, online sugar-related content yields valuable information on the social construction and morality of health and nutrition discourses and the misleading, confusing and overwhelming nature of social media content. Parents' discussions are an example of the general dilemmas between (gendered) parenting expectations, individual freedom and morality of food choices.

Key words: Sugar, parents, food choices, social media, netnography, family health, dietary cacophony, Social Judgment Theory

Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), childhood obesity has reached epidemic proportions and is among the most serious public health challenges of the 21st century (World Health Organization, 2016). Although obesity is a complex and multifactorial condition, diets high in added sugar have been linked to increased frequency of obesity in children, as well as in adults (Hu, 2013; Lichtenstein et al., 2006; Livesey, 2011; Ludwig, Peterson, & Gortmaker, 2001). Therefore, the WHO calls on countries to reduce sugar intake among adults and children due to evidence of the effect of intake of free sugars on overweight, obesity and also on tooth decay (World Health Organization, 2015b).

As the main gatekeepers of children's food intake, parents are frequently the object of health-related discussions on sugar reduction initiated by health professionals and authorities. Parents, indeed, influence the development of children's eating behaviors and weight status and shape early learning about food and eating (Birch & Ventura, 2009). Certainly, the dietary beliefs and attitudes that parents propagate to children are influenced by their own experiences and cultural traditions

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(Birch & Ventura, 2009). What parents consider healthy or unhealthy varies according to culture, social context, access to information and interpretation of this information (Hébel, 2010).

In-depth qualitative studies with parents have revealed a certain mistrust of public health nutrition messages on the grounds of parents' confusion (Bianchi et al., 2016; Elliott & Bowen, 2018; O'Key & Hugh-Jones, 2010). This confusion is exacerbated in a digital era, where online nutrition information from diverse sources spread quickly. The unique advantages of the internet and social media (fast, interactive, anonymous) have led parents to search for and rely on online dietary and nutrition information to an ever-increasing degree (Bianco, Zucco, Nobile, Pileggi, & Pavia, 2013; Chen, Aram, & Tannenbaum, 2014). Unfortunately, a great share of the information on social media is not evidence based, as government and non-profit groups are less likely to have social media profiles and to engage with users (Lovejoy, Waters, & Saxton, 2012).

Therefore, parents are exposed to various, sometimes misleading and conflicting information on dietary issues (Porter & Ispa, 2013). For example, in the current public debate about sugar, there is a great amount of information on the very concept of what sugar means. Although the WHO explains: "Free sugars refer to monosaccharides and disaccharides added to foods and beverages by the manufacturer, cook or consumer, and sugars naturally present in honey, syrups, fruit juices and fruit juice concentrates" (World Health Organization, 2015a, p. 4), the complexity of information available online and on food labels create confusion among consumers. It is reported that sugar appears with 56 different names on food product ingredient lists (Lustig, 2013). How consumers, including parents, interpret and apply the definitions, concepts and recommendations around sugar is an under-explored area.

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Consumer and behavioral studies have demonstrated that in spite of the common knowledge in health sciences worldwide, what individuals consider as healthy is to a great extent socio-culturally constructed (Bisogni, Jastran, Seligson, & Thompson, 2012; Hébel, 2010). In fact, in earlier qualitative research comparing discourses of French and Danish parents, we identified cultural differences in the meanings attributed to sugar (Moura & Aschemann-Witzel, 2020). This prior analysis revealed that whereas Danish parents tended to consider sugar a source of energy, reward and comfort, French parents often expressed to fear sugar as a dangerous and addictive substance. This contrasting approach instigated our curiosity to explore the sugar perceptions across those two countries further and with additional methods.

In Denmark there is a tradition called “*Fredagslik*”, literally meaning Friday Candy, where families have a cozy time together enjoying candies and other comfort foods (Gram & Grønhøj, 2015). This tradition is related to the concept of “*hygge*” that involves a category of practices to create a cozy atmosphere, also including the consumption of sweets (Linnet, 2011). The word *hygge* has become famous through a range of book publications (Brits, 2017; Russell, 2015; Wiking, 2016). Although culinary traditions in France do involve sweet preparations (desserts, pastries), there is less emphasis on confectionaries and other processed sugary products in the French culinary culture (Tebben, 2008). This study builds on and further extends the understanding of these cross-country differences, and how they are represented in parental discourses.

Acknowledging that the meanings attributed to food ingredients vary across nations (Saint-Pol, 2015), this study aims to provide insights into the dietetic beliefs and rationale behind sugar consumption among families in two distinct countries. Considering the impact of excessive sugar intake on human health and childhood obesity as well as the fact that parents’ beliefs are important

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to consider as part of obesity treatment (Lovell, 2016), this study aimed at gaining further understanding of connotations, perceptions and attitudes about sugar among parents. We focus on discourses to capture symbol systems and social motivations related to the phenomena studied (Deetz, 2003). This contribution is important for the well-being of families and for stakeholders involved in public health nutrition campaigns. From a social marketing perspective (an approach increasingly applied in nutrition campaigns), investigating the language of the target group is crucial for tailor-made interventions targeting behavior change (Kohli & Jaworski, 1990; Luecking et al., 2017).

A qualitative research approach using social media content was applied. The exploration of this topic on social media allows a unique perspective on parental discourses that has not been explored in the literature so far. Social media have become a major form of communication allowing spontaneous expression of attitudes, views and opinions, and have been largely used in consumer behavior studies (Branthwaite & Patterson, 2011).

Data were set in a Social Judgment Theory (SJT) analytical framework. The SJT is a theory of persuasion applied to understand the ways individuals evaluate a topic of discussion and publicly spread messages (Sherif, Sherif, & Nebergall, 1965); for instance, it has been used to evaluate the communication of food-related health behaviors (Rumble, Lundy, Martin, & Anderson, 2017).

The SJT suggests that knowing a person's attitudes on subjects can provide clues about how to approach a persuasive effort (Dainton & Zelle, 2004). From a Social Judgment Theory standpoint, individuals may accept, reject or non-commit to public persuasive messages on the basis of their ego-involvement with the topic (relation of the topic with core values and concept of self).

Data and Methods

The present analysis follows a social listening practice (Stewart & Arnold, 2018), including aspects of ethnographic techniques described by Kozinets (2002). This technique is developed through the following steps: cultural entrée in which the research topics are formulated and the online channels identified that might inform about these topics; ethical data collection and analysis, and meaningful representation of the data (Kozinets, 2002). Below, we describe the choice of online channels, data collection procedure, analysis and presentation; including ethical considerations.

Choice of social media

Previous studies have observed that parents, especially mothers, increase the frequency and intensity of social media use during the transition to parenthood (Bartholomew, Schoppe-Sullivan, Glassman, Kamp Dush, & Sullivan, 2012). Mothers use digital media (websites, blogs and social media platforms) passively to obtain information and support, but also to express their opinions, acting as co-creators of digital data (Lupton, 2016).

Facebook is the dominant and most widely used social media platform in France and Denmark, with 53 percent of Danish internet users turning to Facebook on a daily basis. Since the majority of active Facebook users in both countries are in their childbearing years (18-34-year-olds), it is likely that a large number of users are parents (Statista Research Department, 2019; The Danish Agency for Culture and Palaces, 2018). Parental blogs are also fairly popular among new parents (McDaniel, Coyne, & Holmes, 2012), and like Facebook, do not have a word limit for content posted. Therefore, a thematic analysis of sugar-related posts and comments on blogs and Facebook groups and pages for parents was performed.

Data collection

Data collection began in September 2019 by identifying French and Danish language blogs and Facebook pages with explicit food-related content for parents. A search was conducted in the message board of groups discussing the following key words: sugar, sugary, sweets or candy(ies) (in French: *sucre*, *sucré(e)*, *sucrierie*, *bonbons*; in Danish: *sukker*, which has a broad meaning, including sugar and sugary. Danish words for sweets and candies – *søde sager*, *slik* – did not lead to new data). Posts, shared URLs, photos, comments and conversations in which the key words were mentioned were copied for analysis.

Since French is a language spoken in many countries other than France, measures were taken to maximize the chances of collecting data from parents living in France. Each time a relevant content appeared from a page whose administrator was not from France, the lead researcher sought to verify the author's location (sometimes publicly available). Messages from people identified to be from other French-speaking countries were excluded from the analysis. Messages from people whose location was not publicly available, were also excluded. In the remainder of the manuscript, the wording "French/Danish parents" is used for text simplification.

The data also comprised sugar-related content outside Facebook and blogs that were repeatedly shared by parents. External sources included one documentary and the content of two TV shows, resulting in 10 pages of content with researchers' reflective notes. The final data set included a word file with 59,854 words from France, and a word file with 41,232 words from Denmark.

In order to enhance the credibility and confirmability of the findings (the degree to which the results could be confirmed and corroborated), an interview with one expert in each country was carried out as a means of data triangulation (Kozinets, 2010). The expert was chosen after the

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analysis of the social media content, and the choice is therefore based on the cross-country emerging differences. In France, the social scientist Claude Fischler was contacted due to his extensive research on attitudes towards sugar in the French population (Fischler, 1987, 1988), including mothers (Fischler, 1986). In Denmark, an in-depth interview was conducted with the anthropologist Jeppe Trolle Linnet, who is specialized in Danish consumer culture and *hygge* (Linnet, 2011) (since *hygge* was a recurrent theme in the Danish data). A semi-structured interview guide was developed (Appendix), and the interviews were conducted by phone, in English. Both interviews were transcribed verbatim.

Ethical considerations

To ensure ethical research practices the current study drew on the guidelines of the Association of Internet Researchers (Franzke, Bechmann, Zimmer, Ess, & the Association of Internet Researchers, 2020), and was approved by Aarhus University ethics committee (Serial Number: 2019-280). The analysis was restricted to pages and groups where no acceptance was required. Groups that were 'locked' to non-members were deemed unsuitable for analysis. The quotations selected to present the data (in italics in the text) were translated into English and slightly modified (while preserving meaning and tone) to ensure that quotes cannot be traced back to members through major search engines. Lastly, no personally identifiable information and/or sensitive data (European Commission, 2016) was collected, only narratives and self-reported information on food choices, consumer behavior and daily mundane activities related to food.

Data analysis and presentation

Posts, comments and interview transcripts were copied into a Word file and exported to the NVivo software to facilitate coding and analysis. An inductive approach was employed, meaning that

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themes were generated from the data through open coding before returning to the literature and using theories deductively to identify certain themes (Gale, Heath, Cameron, Rashid, & Redwood, 2013).

Data gathering and thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) were conducted following three main steps: 1) Broad codes were generated from the first posts and comments to build up an initial coding frame; 2) As new data and insights unfolded, new content matched existing codes and new codes were created; 3) Potential themes and sub-themes were generated from the codes (see online supplementary material); 4) Themes and sub-themes were constantly revised, and a first thematic “map” of the analysis was created (Figure 1). An iterative process including continuous reading of the content, refining codes, and re-coding was followed until central and salient themes were identified. It was noted that no new themes emerged on coding the final data gathered, thus implying theoretical saturation (Locke, 2000).

Insights from the expert interviews were integrated into the analysis after the coding of the social media data, helping to deepen the understating of the codes and themes uncovered. All the content was initially coded by the first author and reliability checks were done by the research assistant involved in the data collection and the second author. Both authors met several times to discuss emerging results.

It is important to mention that the initial cycles of data analysis gave rise to the groups of the Social Judgment Theory (SJT): acceptance, non-commitment and rejection. Although the data are presented alongside elements of the SJT, the different approaches to sugar were uncovered inductively and existed before the relevance of the SJT analysis became apparent to the researchers.

Themes and sub-themes were represented in mind maps (Figures 1 and 2) and are discussed in the text (in bold). Quotes (in italics) were selected to reflect the different beliefs, attitudes and meanings, attributed to sugar and reaction to anti-sugar messages. The specific extracts were selected on the basis that they illustrated a variety of opinions, including stances which were salient, unusual, or quotes that represented a concise summary of a discussion topic. Words between brackets were added to provide context where needed, and three bracketed dots mean that part of the sentence was taken out.

It is important to highlight that given the netnographic approach, the data are based primarily on the observation and theoretical analysis of textual discourses, not including actual behaviors and practices (Kozinets, 2002). Subsequently, the present analysis focuses on theoretical aspects, seeking for symbolic richness in the expression of the studied phenomena (sugar consumption) through discourses.

Results

The results section is structured as follows: 1) Sugar-related concerns, meanings and beliefs, divided into two subsections (parent-focused and child-focused content), 2) Attitudes to online content on sugar (referring to the Social Judgment Theory approach).

Sugar-related concerns, meanings and beliefs

The major themes and subthemes regarding concerns, meanings and beliefs are presented in Figure 1. The themes most relevant for the research question are explored in the text (bold).

Figure 1. Mind-map of sugar-related themes and sub-themes uncovered in the data analysis. The lines connect ideas but the length does not represent importance.

Parent-focused content

Pregnancy: Many discussions surrounded the issue of **craving** for sweets during pregnancy, with some mothers defining themselves as very sugary-pregnant. Interestingly, cravings for sweets were suggested by French mothers to indicate the (female) sex of the baby.

French mothers saw efforts of a sugar-free diet as comparable to quitting alcohol or cigarettes. Actually, cravings were a main theme among mothers who tried **smoke cessation**. Among the recurrent strategies for dealing with pregnancy cravings were the consumption of **fruit, nuts**, and

sugar replacers (mainly stevia). Products like coconut sugar and sugar cane were considered good alternatives to beet sugar, for being “whole”, “complete” and “non-synthetic”. The use of **artificial sweeteners** was extensively discussed among French mothers, mainly as a source of fear and confusion. Most of the comments in this regard expressed frustration about the impossibility of making the right choice. One person summarized the discouragement when facing nutrition dilemmas, when s/he wrote:

“I stopped [eating aspartame] for two years because I had read that aspartame could have an impact on the development of the genitals of the fetus (especially boys) and could lead to sterility. [...]. And then if I have a craving [for sugar], I prefer to drink a small glass of classic soda. Anyway, soda also has something to do with osteoporosis ... You have to make a choice.”

Weight loss and sugar-free diet: Sugar consumption appeared as one of the main barriers for weight loss, and mothers shared tips on how to succeed in a low-sugar/sugar-free diet. “Abstaining” from sugar for a certain period was also seen as advantageous to “detox” and “purify” the body. Sugar was framed as toxic, evil and a “real drug”. Expressions like “abstinence period” “weaning from sugar”, “getting clean” reinforced the drug addiction metaphors.

From an extreme position, some French mothers excluded **fruit** from their sugar-free diet for weight loss. This pattern was absent among Danish mothers who recurrently wrote phrases like: “*Fruit sugar does not count as sugar*”. In fact, although in Denmark sugar was also framed as unhealthy and addictive, the sugar-free period appeared to be more flexible, allowing to include sugar in preparations (e.g. sugar in oatmeal). The fear of being “too sanctimonious” about a sugar-free diet was common in the Danish discourses.

Religious vocabulary was common in the testimonials describing the challenges of sugar-free experiences, such as “temptation”, “Satan”, “sinful”. The association of sugar with religious terms could be seen as a reflection of the high complexity of a sugar consumption paradox and were confirmed in the words of Claude Fischler. The sociologist sustained that sugar-free diets have gained popularity in recent years and resonate as “stories of salvation” in the media.

Social media conversations reproduced scientific and medical terms such as glycemic index, insulin, carbohydrates. However, the discourses denoted confusion and disagreement on the meaning of those terms and how they can be translated into healthy choices. In particular, the definition of “sugar” was surrounded by confusion and contradiction, leading to openhearted discussions. Both experts interviewed confirm this pattern and believe that the confusion derives from the scientific discourses about “sugars”, in plural.

Negative emotions: Sugar cravings were often related to negative emotions (e.g. stress, boredom, sadness, anger). The **hedonic and symbolic** value of sugar was evoked, related to comfort, taste and pleasure during adverse situations and mood swings. Among Danish mothers, sugar was casted as a source of energy and emotional **reward**, helping to overcome hangovers and also fatigue: “[...] *on maternity leave with a baby that has kept me awake almost continuously for five months, I'll not survive without something sweet*”.

In Denmark, as confirmed by Jeppe Linnet “*the attitudes, practices and the discourses of Danish parents about sugar are very much centered on the concept of hygge*”. *Hygge* helps to bring happiness to everyday life and to create a “*free space where everyone is sharing something like goodies, showing each other that we really don't like to be so much in control all the time*” (Jeppe Linnet). This cultural trend was explored (and criticized) in the following quote from a mother:

“There are probably many reasons [for high sugar intake among Danish children]. Both ignorance and certainly something cultural as well. We ourselves have learned that the highly valued “Danish coziness” equals stuffing unhealthy things in our mouths. And now we teach our children this...”

Child-focused content

Festivities: The offering of sugar and candies during celebrations like Easter, Halloween and Christmas was a recurrent topic of concern in online discussions. The opinions diverged in the extremes (from total restriction to total liberation) but mostly including the idea of **moderation**. Socialized sugar consumption was mostly regarded as legitimate and justifiable.

Restriction was defended mainly in France, where a few mothers stressed the *“lack of sense of these capitalist parties”*. One mother brought up (un)ethical aspects of chocolate production, which in her words *“contributes to increase poverty and inequality in the world”*, bringing sugar consumption to a wider political and social scene.

In the opposite view, there were parents who defended **liberated consumption** of sweets, for whom sweets restriction was an almost cruel deprivation to children. Other arguments included own food upbringing (*“Let our children live their lives ... We all ate it...”*) and the fear of compulsive eating behavior due to restriction.

The fear of compulsive eating was more prominent among Danish mothers, as illustrated by this extract: *“Prohibition and hysteria create little sugar-hungry monsters who cannot control themselves”*. One mother even defended the idea of allowing children to eat candies until they vomit, as a way to learn self-regulation: *“My life experience: let the baby eat candy until he vomits. The child will learn to regulate it himself.”* Certainly, children’s autonomy to learn and decide

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about food choices was commonly encouraged by Danish parents: *“I do not believe that scare campaigns lead to any good, rather there should be a focus on teaching children how to deal with what the “world” offers.* Conversely, French parents seemed to believe more in palate education through healthy eating.

The importance of family bonding with consumption of sweets was often emphasized by Danish parents, mainly referring to **Friday Candy**. Friday Candy as an important family ritual was paramount in the data and confirmed by Jeppe Linnet: *“[Friday Candy] It's kind of a reward ritual where there is this inbuilt exception from everyday discipline. Both in terms of what to eat but also in terms of how you raise your children”.*

Child feeding concerns: French parents recurrently exchanged information about the composition and (un)healthiness of **highly processed foods**. How much sugar to allow children appeared as a source of confusion and anxiety. Recommendations from various **knowledge sources**, mainly books, nutrition practitioners and authorities were often mentioned, but did not always appear clearly interpreted.

Distrust in health experts surfaced in the discourses in both countries. Especially in Denmark, some social media users demonstrated skepticism of “rigid” nutrition messages on the grounds that *“there has never been as much focus on sugar, health and weight as today, and never have so many been overweight ...”.*

The most distinct aspect of the French discourses was the **marketing responsibility** for children’s current overconsumption of sugar, especially from **highly processed foods**. **Marketers** were accused of lobbying and anti-ethical strategic methods to *“poison and addict our little ones”.* In

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those discourses, sugar consumption is linked to a broader social perspective, in which sugar is associated with a mischievous food industry that “poisons” consumers in exchange of profit.

This pattern was confirmed by Claude Fischler, who noted that “*there is a general climate of distrust and anger towards food manufacturers and the national institutions*” in the French population. Consumer sovereignty was defended by some mothers, with emphasis on **parental responsibility**, personal autonomy and self-management. Prohibiting sugary products from the market was pointed to as “insane” and “non-sense” by some. This latter position was strongly defended by Danish parents, who also criticized the influence of **schools’ food policies** on individual freedom.

Some schools in Denmark have adopted a “**no-sugar**” **policy**, where parents are not allowed to add any kind of candies to their children’s lunch box, not even for birthday festivities. This policy led to openhearted discussions on the social media, where the majority of the comments criticized the zero-sugar approach as foolish, unnecessary, compulsive-behavior inducing and disregarding parental autonomy. Only a few parents defended **schools’ responsibility** for children’s sugar consumption.

Again (as outlined in the “festivities” theme), three main **behavioral strategies** for dealing with the dilemma of sugar consumption appeared: **restriction**, **moderation** and **liberation**. Restriction was justified on the grounds of the undeniably harmful health effects of sugar. The salient attitude, however, was the invocation of the “everything in moderation” aphorism, where in both countries, **moderation** appears as a general, common and unspecific concept.

There was a third group of parents (rarer in France and more common in Denmark) who claimed not to be worried about sugar consumption. Reasons not to restrict sugar included the importance

given to hedonic and symbolic aspects: “*And I get up every morning and am tempted to put some sugar = love in my son's lunch box*”. Additionally, a great share of the Danish discourses (and some of the French) expressed to value a *healthy, natural, and sensible* relation with sugar, as opposed to a *paranoid, fanatical, hysterical* attitude. A few parents called attention to the fact that “*there are worse things in food than sugar*”, referring mostly to high-in-fat products (e.g. salami). This attitude is explained by what Claude Fischler calls a conflict between “lipophobic” versus “saccharophobic” debates that has been going on since the 80s. According to Fischler, most of the contemporary food-related anxiety is derived from the scientific controversy pointing at either sugar or fat as the main cause of cardiovascular diseases; and the “side taken” in this debate varies from country to country. Indeed, in the present analysis, the French seemed to be more “saccharophobic”, whereas the Danes leaned more towards a “lipophobic” attitude. Fischler points to reasons that go beyond nutrition (e.g. political and economic interests) as accounting for the cross-country difference in public health opinions.

Social aspects. A popular post in France (154 comments, 28 shares) described a situation where a mother was judged by a stranger at the supermarket for denying to buy chocolate for her child.

The discussions following this post raised the issue of an unescapable **societal judgment** on parental role and practices. Parents (mostly mothers) carry ultimate culpability for the health of their children and are criticized for being either too strict or too permissive. The judgmental, moral tone towards parents who restrict sugar, appeared to be more pronounced and to involve more harsh words in Denmark, as for example: “*I'm a sugar-scared, fanatical witch. But that's fine with me*”. The terminology employed in this comment outlines the stigmatization of the ones who dare to publically admit their worries about sugar consumption.

Attitudes to online content on sugar

In France, the external content shared by parents (sugar-related content outside Facebook and blogs) mostly called attention to the **detrimental health effects of sugar**, portraying sugar as a hazard. The information was endorsed by **health experts** and their patients' testimonials in an alarming tone of warning (Figure 2). In Denmark, sugar-related content had a less negative approach. In particular, a magazine interview article with a nutritionist mentioned sugar as a source of energy defending (moderated) sugar consumption as long as it does not compromise the intake of healthy foods. This position was repeatedly reinforced in the comments of Danish parents, who also pointed out babies' inner fondness of sugar as an indication of its healthiness.

In both countries, sugar-related content on social media and parents' reaction to it point to an overabundance of dietary information, which is often complicated, conflicting and overwhelming, what Claude Fischler defines as "**dietary cacophony**". Illustrative extracts include: "*I find it quite difficult to make sense of all that I hear about food today*"; "*Eating is stressful, we feel guilty and we are afraid of everything we swallow ...*". In reaction to the overabundance of mostly anti-sugar messages, parents displayed a range of attitudes, which fell into the three categories of the Social Judgment Theory (acceptance, non-commitment and rejection) and coincided with the three approaches to sugar revealed in the comments (restriction, moderation and liberation), as illustrated in Figure 2 and explained in the text below.

Figure 2: Online content on sugar and main reactions to it, linked to the three types of discourses and attitudes identified in the data analysis. The three colors (orange, yellow and green) represent the different attitudes identified by the concepts described in the horizontal lines (reactions to the content, values and concepts of self, etc.). *SJT: Social Judgment Theory

Acceptance: The parents who demonstrated **assimilation** and acceptance of the messages, describing sugar as a health hazard, were the ones who advocated for sugar **restriction** (more pertinent among the French). The content seemed to conform to members' core values and concept of self, also among a few Danish parents ("I am a low carb mom"), especially as a (responsible) parent: "Unfortunately, Denmark is one of the countries in the world where children eat sugar the most... and I think that is actually a bit embarrassing, but also irresponsible". Some discourses among the group of accepters, attempted to persuade other individuals to also comply with the anti-sugar messages, as in the following extract: "YES we must ban foods that are unhealthy, there are so many !!!! Take responsibility for your own diet, stop avoiding guilt by telling yourself that your children will eat [sugary products] anyway later ... damn".

Non-commitment: Indifference and neutrality towards anti-sugar messages were mainly manifested by the defense of moderated consumption. The anti-sugar pronouncements were deemed questionable on the grounds that nothing that is consumed in **moderation** can be harmful. Mostly, this group of parents showed a weak ego-involvement with the messages, expressing phrases like: “*Parents who want to give sugar to their children, great! The ones who don’t want, great too!*”.

Rejection: A third group of parents rejected the anti-sugar messages. Public discourses on sugar avoidance (mostly the discourses in France) were considered moralistic, judgmental, fanatical and impossible to follow. The alarming tone was seen “*a pretext to make parents feel guilty*” and to arouse constant sense of insecurity and danger.

Parents in the rejection group demonstrated feeling threatened in their behavioral freedoms and reacted by heavily opposing the advised behavior (sugar avoidance). Statements like: “*Now I will give them [the children] even more [sugar]*” expresses the position of rebellion as a counterpoint to official biomedical standpoints. Above all, a healthy-eating identity was depreciated by this group, who frequently criticized who they defined (in a tone of depreciation) as “ecological-dietetic-conscious”, “moralizers”, “healthy-mommies mafia”, “sugar-scared zombies”, “perfect-glycemic-index parents”.

Discussion

The study explored the ways in which representations about sugar are produced in parents’ discourses on French and Danish Facebook pages and blogs. The analysis unfolded a myriad of sociological factors involving official biomedical paradigms, marketing actors, consumers’ agency

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and institutions. It corroborates the notion that the definition of what is healthy in our society is ideologically and sociologically complex, and saturated with moral, political and economic values (Kristensen, Lim, & Askegaard, 2016).

Sugar consumption was portrayed as a two-sided experience, being at the same time virtuous and sinful, harmful and delightful. Sugar thus represents a dilemma in everyday food choices, to which individuals might respond with morally dichotomous attitudes: self-control vs. compulsion, asceticism vs. indulgence, safety vs. exposure to danger (Leipämaa-Leskinen, 2007b).

The sugar paradox was previously brought forward by the Danish researchers Kristensen and Johansen (2018) in a sociological analysis of the “sugar addiction” phenomenon in Denmark. For those authors, the dilemma about sugar denounces the high complexity and ambivalence of modern consumer culture itself, being a metaphor “*for the potential danger of the moral and bodily decay of the proper human in modern consumer society*”. In our analysis, the criticism towards “capitalist parties” involving sugar (that a few mothers claimed about Easter, Halloween, Christmas) is in line with this reflection.

Three main behavioral strategies emerged as a response to the sugar dilemma, that corresponded to the three attitudes of the SJT: acceptance, non-commitment and rejection of conflicting public messages. The discourses of the individuals who **accepted** the anti-sugar messages, echoed aspects of the sociological notion of healthism, explored by Crawford (1980). For Crawford, *healthists* (adopters of the healthism ideology) take private and personal responsibility for their own health, which in turn depends on moral motivation to resist culture, marketing strategies, political and environmental constraints (Crawford, 1980). Healthism is thus grounded on neoliberal ethos, where citizens take responsibility for their own bodies and encourage others to do the same. In a

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healthist neoliberal landscape, some individuals differentiate themselves as the ones who fulfil their moral obligations, steering away from temptations, and opposing to those who do not (Kristensen et al., 2016).

This moral distinction was clear in the social media comments from one group to the other (mainly accepters versus rejecters). The **rejecters** seem to resist the healthism imperative and challenge the doctor-patient hierarchy. Individuals who expressed an attitude of rejection seemed to manage to “break free” of social forces and enjoy the pleasures of the socially condemned sugar (Kristensen & Johansen, 2018). This “freedom” from the healthism imperative appears to derive from (among other factors) distrust and anger towards health authorities and the state. Indeed, the capitalistic landscape is deemed to generate distrust in the contemporary citizen for reducing individuals to a mere workforce, which is manifested in the constant emphasis on the costs of non-productive citizens (e.g. ill or retired people) (Kristensen et al., 2016). Interestingly, both accepters and rejecters seem to oppose aspects of a neoliberal capitalist social order: accepters by the criticism and distrust in the food industry, and rejecters by opposing health experts and institutions’ power and authority.

Although a distinction between three categories appeared in social, it is important to consider the plurality of individuals as eater and consumers, capable of adapting attitudes and practices to the moment in life and context (Bisogni, Jastran, Shen, & Devine, 2005; Fischler, 1980). As the data presented here confirm, the contemporary Western consumer navigates between ascetical self-discipline and an epicurean pursuit of pleasure (in this case, through food) (Leipämaa-Leskinen, 2007a). Since contradiction is considered inseparable of the human condition, and therefore of consumption, individuals shift between the two value conflicts (asceticism vs. hedonism),

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according to situational cues and structural norms (Leipämaa-Leskinen, 2007a). In this extant, the non-committer category might be a stance that both accepters and rejecters fall in and out of, as a strategy to manage the moral conflict of food choices.

In regard to more polarized attitudes, the cross-country analysis showed that restriction was commonly defended among the French. French parents' apparent asceticism may seem, at a first glance, contrary to what has been described in the literature. The French culture is characterized as giving higher value to the hedonic aspects of food, and to focus less on nutrition aspects compared to other countries (Rozin, Fischler, Imada, Sarubin, & Wrzesniewski, 1999). Nevertheless, the current study reveals that the "sacharophobia" among French parents refers to mainly the "hidden" sugar in highly processed foods, recognized to lack nutrition, gastronomic and cultural value. In fact, the French population's distrust in food agencies has previously been documented (Fournier & Poulain, 2018) and may account for the anger expressed towards the food industry. This contrasts with the high social trust observed in the Danish culture, which extends to citizens' trust in public and private institutions (Sønderskov & Dinesen, 2014). However, in both settings, homemade desserts appeared as an alternative to sensory pleasure in a society permeated by industrial influence and artificiality (Kristensen & Johansen, 2018).

The findings highlight the dietary confusion that the contemporary consumer experiences due to information overload, or *dietary cacophony*, a classic mechanism identified since the 80's (Fischler, 1995). Overload of negative nutrition messages focusing on dichotomous (good/bad) classifications cause feelings of impotence, leading to rejection of the message and even repudiation (Freeland-Graves & Nitzke, 2013; Sherif et al., 1965, p. 13). The inner conflict generated by a message that is too discrepant from the receivers' position and possibilities and

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requires a great deal of attitude change, can indeed, cause a “boomerang” attitude (i.e. an attitude change in the direction opposite that advocated), as some parents manifested in the data gathered (O’Keefe, 2015, p. 25; Sherif et al., 1965, p. 13).

The adoption of a “rebellious” attitude on social media appeared as a reaction to a message that seemed practically unfeasible, but also authoritarian and morally judgmental. Certainly, food choices have become a window through which not only the morality of individuals’ choices is evaluated, but also the moral character of the individuals themselves (Crossley, 2002; Kristensen et al., 2016). It is striking that moralistic tones were also directed at “too-healthy” parents, revealing the constant and inescapable social judgment of parents as regards to child-feeding practices. Social judgment of “too-healthy” parents was more pronounced in Denmark, which could be a reflection of the cultural concept of law of *Jante*. This cultural code of conduct denotes a disapproval of any kind of fanaticism or ambition to perfection (Linnet, 2011). Indeed, objection to strict dietary control, often portrayed as “fanatical”, was also identified in discourses about fat among Danish consumers (Askegaard, Jensen, & Holt, 1999).

It is of particular significance that, apparently, only mothers joined the pages and discussions in all data collected. The low involvement of fathers in online discussion on children’s issues is confirmed by other studies (Chen 2014; Radey & Randolph 2009) and might reflect the low level of fathers’ engagement in children’s healthy feeding practices (Khandpur, Blaine, Fisher, & Davison, 2014).

Another nuance of gender issues in the data was the associating of sweet cravings during pregnancy as a signal of a baby girl. This finding gains further significance from a socio-historical perspective. At the beginning of the 20th century, sugar started to be associated with girls through

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sexist stereotypes, as explained by Abbot (2008) “*like sugar, girls were innately sweet; also like sugar, which lacked nutrition value, girls were frivolous and impractical*” (Abbott, 2008, p. 372).

The “feminization” of sugar occurred when it became cheap and recognized as an unhealthy ingredient. As a result, the feminization of sugar contributed to the objectification of women and girls, undervaluing them like a cheap commodity (Woloson, 2002). Women and girls were then associated with being “sweet”, “decorative” and “empty”.

In closing this discussion, we note that the repeated concerns about child feeding practices denoted aspects of biomedicalization. A child's body (especially the female body) is biomedicalized in our society, meaning that it is defined as a medical condition requiring expert intervention (Cozzi & Vinel, 2015; Fassin, 2013). Through their discourses and the raised dilemmas about child feeding, mothers demonstrated internalizing the ideology that children require care and intervention from health authorities. The hierarchization involved in contemporary child health care, placing children as passive victims, implies viewing adults (mostly mothers) as guilty of their children's health issues (Fassin, 2013; O'Key & Hugh-Jones, 2010).

Implications for practice and research

Through online written expression, parents revealed the way they reinforce or disrupt the extant public health messages about sugar consumption, and the framework of the Social Judgment Theory has helped to understand the reasoning behind individuals' attitudes to the issue. Aligned with the SJT postulations, the same message was perceived differently according to individuals' ego-involvement with the content, values and self-concept issues, which influenced the distinct approaches to sugar (restriction, moderation or liberation). Therefore, the findings indicate a need for diversified measures to tackle sugar consumption among families. For the highly involved

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individuals, maintenance of healthful eating habits can be encouraged. However, possible side-effects of a too-restrictive approach (i.e. disordered eating, avoidance of fresh fruit) should be considered.

Individuals in the high ego-involvement and acceptance category also demonstrated potential for persuading other individuals to adopt their standpoints. This might be an interesting insight for public health campaigns, considering that self-persuasion (in this case, parents persuading other parents) is more effective than direct persuasion in increasing healthy eating behaviors (Bernritter, van Ooijen, & Müller, 2017). Self-persuasion seems indeed an important avenue to explore, especially considering the mistrust in institutions emphasized in the discourses.

Notably, the non-involved consumers carry great potential for persuasion (O'Keefe, 2015, p. 22). Individuals with a non-involved attitude are not averse to anti-sugar/health messages and might be influenced to change behavior in a healthier direction through increased self-efficacy, capability enhancement and clarification of confusing information. In particular, recommendations from health authorities could be more easily translated into practical guidance that considers the plurality of individuals in terms of social and psychological wellbeing. For example, the use of popular terms instead of scientific ones (e.g. table sugar versus sugar in whole grain foods rather than simple and complex carbohydrates), recommendations in terms of foods as opposed to nutrients (e.g. maximum advised amount of candies, rather than the quantity of free sugars a day). Equally important, the hedonic and symbolic value attributed to sugar should not be neglected in nutrition counselling. Additionally, nutrition guidelines could include specific guidance for traditional celebrations in which sugar consumption is involved (e.g. the ritual of Friday Candy in Denmark).

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The existence of a “transgressive” audience points to the need to respect individuals’ desire for independence, freedom of mind and hedonism. Small substantial changes over time might be accomplished by this group, once their values and self-identity are acknowledged (O’Keefe, 2015, pp. 22-25).

In all stances, professionals should be aware of the high susceptibility of health sciences to reflect moral judgment and prejudices of the cultural, historical and social context (Fassin, 2011). Therefore, policy makers (and researchers) should not disregard the prevailing moral agenda on food and health that compromises consumers’ wellbeing, and be more reflexive on the political constructions behind scientific and/or public truths (Askegaard et al., 2014).

Strengths, limitations and future research

To the best of the authors’ knowledge, this is the first cross-national study to explore the meanings of sugar attributed by parents on social media platforms. The analysis was strengthened by examining the discourses through the lens of the Social Judgment Theory. It is important to highlight though that the SJT framework helped to emphasize the two categories in the extremes of attitudes: acceptance and rejection. It is reasonable to assume that most individuals who fall in the non-committers category, who are neutral to the subject, are not part of the social media discussions; thus, were not substantially represented in the content analyzed.

The “naturally occurring” discourses enabled gathering data without researcher bias, in an entirely unobtrusive and naturalistic manner (Bergman, Eli, Osowski, Lövestam, & Nowicka, 2019; Kozinets, 2002). However, for ethical reasons, no socio-demographic data of users was obtained. Therefore, like in most studies examining social media activity, the study lacks information on how representative parents who interact on blogs and Facebook are, regarding the general parent

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population in their respective societies. Data triangulation (with expert interviews) was employed in order to decrease the narrowness of the findings (Kozinets, 2002). Furthermore, as Kozinets (2002) points out (evoking the ideas of the early sociologist George Herbert Mead), the ultimate unit of analysis in netnography might not be the individual, but the behavior or act (Kozinets, 2002).

Another important limitation is the reliance on researcher interpretive skills (Kozinets, 2002), which was addressed by discussion of reflective field notes. Nevertheless, it is worth mentioning a few things on the authors' moral standpoints that inevitably influence the analysis. The authors favor feminist and Marxist ideologies. As such, we lean towards raising awareness on women's social injustices and towards hidden agendas in health policies that serve corporate interest. Paradoxically, by choosing to focus on a single ingredient that is nutritionally classified as unhealthy, we must admit a certain influence of the moral food dichotomy ideology in our approach (for an interesting discussion on this, see Askegaard et al., 2014).

One limitation regarding our "sample" was the possibility for anonymization on social media. Anonymization might lead individuals to shift personality expression in order to influence the representation of online self, thus, influencing the veracity of information posted (Kozinets, 2002). Nevertheless, on platforms like Facebook, where individuals usually know their audience from outside the internet, there is a tendency to express traits that align with the offline self (Sloan & Quan-Haase, 2017, p. 78).

As mentioned in the methods section, the present analysis focused on textual discourses, meanings and symbol systems rather than on actual practices. Although language evokes the highly complex character of food intake and is a valuable indirect tool for investigating behaviors and attitudes

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(Fischler, 1990), further research is needed to evaluate the actual relation of online sugar-related content with families' eating behaviors.

Conclusion

Through social media discourses, French and Danish parents revealed paradoxes, inner and social conflicts on how to negotiate their and their children's bodies, identities and values in the realm of a "sugar dilemma".

According to the pertinent meaning attributed to sugar (danger versus pleasure), ego-involvement with the content, values and self-concept issues, three main judgmental attitudes (acceptance, non-commitment and rejection) and respective behavioral strategies (restriction, moderation and liberation) were demonstrated in the online discourses. In terms of country differences, it appears that restriction was more prominent in France, while liberation was more prominent in Denmark. Findings then imply a need to adapt health messages according to individuals' attitudes, social context, culture and value systems when targeting parents and families' sugar consumption.

Online sugar-related content yields valuable information on the social construction and morality of health and nutrition imperatives and the misleading, confusing and overwhelming nature of social media content. Parents' discussions are an example of the general dilemmas between (gendered) parenting expectations, individual freedom and morality of food choices.

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References

- Abbott, E. (2008). *Sugar: A Bittersweet History*. Canada: Penguin
- Askegaard, S., Jensen, A. F., & Holt, D. B. (1999). Lipophobia: A transatlantic concept? *ACR: The Association for Consumer Research*, 26(NA - Advances in Consumer Research).
- Askegaard, S., Ordabayeva, N., Chandon, P., Cheung, T., Chytikova, Z., Cornil, Y., . . . Junghans, A. F. (2014). Moralities in food and health research. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 30(17-18), 1800-1832. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/0267257X.2014.959034>
- Bartholomew, M. K., Schoppe-Sullivan, S. J., Glassman, M., Kamp Dush, C. M., & Sullivan, J. M. (2012). New parents' Facebook use at the transition to parenthood. *Family Relations*, 61(3), 455-469. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1741-3729.2012.00708.x>
- Bergman, K., Eli, K., Osowski, C. P., Lövestam, E., & Nowicka, P. (2019). Public expressions of trust and distrust in governmental dietary advice in Sweden. *Qualitative Health Research*, 29(8), 1161-1173. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732318825153>
- Bernritter, S. F., van Ooijen, I., & Müller, B. C. (2017). Self-persuasion as marketing technique: the role of consumers' involvement. *European Journal of Marketing*.
- Bianchi, C. M., Huneau, J. F., Le Goff, G., Verger, E. O., Mariotti, F., & Gurviez, P. (2016). Concerns, attitudes, beliefs and information seeking practices with respect to nutrition-related issues: a qualitative study in French pregnant women. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth*, 16(1), 1-14. doi:<http://10.1186/s12884-016-1078-6>
- Bianco, A., Zucco, R., Nobile, C. G. A., Pileggi, C., & Pavia, M. (2013). Parents seeking health-related information on the Internet: cross-sectional study. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 15(9), e204. doi:<http://doi:10.2196/jmir.2752>
- Birch, L., & Ventura, A. (2009). Preventing childhood obesity: what works? *International Journal of Obesity*, 33(S1), S74-S81. doi:<http://10.1038/ijo.2009.22>
- Bisogni, C. A., Jastran, M., Seligson, M., & Thompson, A. (2012). How people interpret healthy eating: contributions of qualitative research. *Journal of Nutrition Education and Behavior*, 44(4), 282-301. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jneb.2011.11.009>

- Moura, A. F., & Aschemann-Witzel, J. (2021). Perspectives on sugar consumption expressed on social media by French-speaking and Danish-speaking parents. *Social Science & Medicine*, 270, 113636. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2020.113636>
- Bisogni, C. A., Jastran, M., Shen, L., & Devine, C. M. (2005). A biographical study of food choice capacity: Standards, circumstances, and food management skills. *Journal of Nutrition Education and Behavior*, 37(6), 284-291. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S1499-4046\(06\)60158-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1499-4046(06)60158-9)
- Branthwaite, A., & Patterson, S. (2011). The power of qualitative research in the era of social media. *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 14(4), 430-440. doi: <http://10.1108/135227511111163245>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77-101. doi:<http://10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Brits, L. T. (2017). *The Book of Hygge: The Danish Art of Contentment, Comfort, and Connection*. US: Penguin.
- Chen, P., Aram, D., & Tannenbaum, M. (2014). Forums for parents of young children: Parents' online conversations in Israel and France. *International Journal About Parents in Education*, 8(1).
- Cozzi, D., & Vinel, V. (2015). Risky, early, controversial. Puberty in medical discourses. *Social Science & Medicine*, 143, 287-296. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2014.11.018>
- Crawford, R. (1980). Healthism and the medicalization of everyday life. *International Journal of Health Services*, 10(3), 365-388. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2190/3H2H-3XJN-3KAY-G9NY>
- Crossley, M. L. (2002). 'Could you please pass one of those health leaflets along?': Exploring health, morality and resistance through focus groups. *Social Science & Medicine*, 55(8), 1471-1483. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536\(01\)00265-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536(01)00265-9)
- Dainton, M., & Zelley, E. (2004). Chapter 5: Explaining theories of persuasion. In *Applying communication theory for professional life: A practical introduction*. La Salle University, USA.
- Deetz, S. (2003). Reclaiming the legacy of the linguistic turn. *Organization*, 10(3), 421-429.
- Elliott, S., & Bowen, S. (2018). Defending motherhood: Morality, responsibility, and double binds in feeding children. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 80(2), 499-520. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jomf.12465>
- European Commission. (2016). *Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council* Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679&from=EN#d1e1489-1-1>. Accessed 18 February 2020.
- Fassin, D. (2011). This is not medicalization. In Geoffrey Hunt & H. Maitena Milhet (Eds.), *Drugs and culture: knowledge, consumption and policy* (pp. 85-93): Routledge.
- Fassin, D. (2013). Children as victims: The moral economy of childhood in the times of AIDS. In J. Biehl & A. Petryna (Eds.), *When people come first: Critical studies in global health* (pp. 109-129): Oxford University Press
- Fischler, C. (1980). Food habits, social change and the nature/culture dilemma. *Social Science Information*, 19(6), 937-953.
- Fischler, C. (1986). Learned versus "spontaneous" dietetics: French mothers' views of what children should eat. *Social Science Information*, 25(4), 945-965. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/053901886025004009>
- Fischler, C. (1987). Attitudes towards sugar and sweetness in historical and social perspective. In J. Dobbing (Ed.), *Sweetness* (pp. 83-98). London: Springer.

- Moura, A. F., & Aschemann-Witzel, J. (2021). Perspectives on sugar consumption expressed on social media by French-speaking and Danish-speaking parents. *Social Science & Medicine*, 270, 113636. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2020.113636>
- Fischler, C. (1988). Les images changeantes du sucre: saccharophilie et saccharophobie. *Journal d'Agriculture Traditionnelle et de Botanique Appliquée*, 35(1), 241-260.
- Fischler, C. (1990). L'omnivore. *Paris, Odile Jacob*, 414.
- Fischler, C. (1995). La cacophonie diététique: Ce que manger veut dire. *L'Ecole des Parents*(5), 2.
- Fournier, T., & Poulain, J.-P. (2018). Eating according to one's genes? Exploring the French public's understanding of and reactions to personalized nutrition. *Qualitative Health Research*, 28(14), 2195-2207.
- Franzke, A. S., Bechmann, A., Zimmer, M., Ess, C., & the Association of Internet Researchers. (2020). *Internet Research: Ethical Guidelines 3.0*. Retrieved from <https://aoir.org/reports/ethics3.pdf>. Accessed 10 January 2020.
- Freeland-Graves, J. H., & Nitzke, S. (2013). Position of the Academy of Nutrition and Dietetics: Total diet approach to healthy eating. *Journal of the Academy of Nutrition and Dietetics*, 113(2), 307-317. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jand.2012.12.013>
- Gale, N. K., Heath, G., Cameron, E., Rashid, S., & Redwood, S. (2013). Using the framework method for the analysis of qualitative data in multi-disciplinary health research. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 13(1), 117. doi:<http://www.biomedcentral.com/1471-2288/13/117>
- Gram, M., & Grønhøj, A. (2015). "There is usually just one Friday a week": Parents' and children's categorizations of "unhealthy" food. *Food, Culture & Society*, 18(4), 547-567. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/15528014.2015.1088189>
- Hébel, P. (2010). Influence de la communication sur l'alimentation. In Presses Universitaires de France (Ed.), *Communication & Langages* (Vol. 2, pp. 41-52). Paris Presses Universitaires de France
- Hu, F. B. (2013). Resolved: There is sufficient scientific evidence that decreasing sugar-sweetened beverage consumption will reduce the prevalence of obesity and obesity-related diseases. *Obesity Reviews*, 14(8), 606-619. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/obr.12040>
- Khandpur, N., Blaine, R. E., Fisher, J. O., & Davison, K. K. (2014). Fathers' child feeding practices: A review of the evidence. *Appetite*, 78, 110-121. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2014.03.015>
- Kohli, A. K., & Jaworski, B. J. (1990). Market orientation: the construct, research propositions, and managerial implications. *Journal of Marketing*, 54(2), 1-18. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/002224299005400201>
- Kozinets, R. V. (2002). The field behind the screen: Using netnography for marketing research in online communities. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 39(1), 61-72. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkr.39.1.61.18935>
- Kozinets, R. V. (2010). *Netnography: Doing ethnographic research online*: Sage publications.
- Kristensen, D. B., & Johansen, K. S. (2018). Self, substance, and society. *Tidsskrift for Forskning I Sygdom Og Samfund*, 15(28), 63-86. doi: <https://doi.org/10.7146/tfss.v15i28.107260>
- Kristensen, D. B., Lim, M., & Askegaard, S. (2016). Healthism in Denmark: State, market, and the search for a "Moral Compass". *Health*, 20(5), 485-504. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1363459316638541>
- Leipämaa-Leskinen, H. (2007a). Contradictions in food consumption. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 31(6), 597-602. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1470-6431.2007.00614.x>
- Leipämaa-Leskinen, H. (2007b). Contradictions in food consumption. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 31(6), 597-602. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1470-6431.2007.00614.x>

- Moura, A. F., & Aschemann-Witzel, J. (2021). Perspectives on sugar consumption expressed on social media by French-speaking and Danish-speaking parents. *Social Science & Medicine*, 270, 113636. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2020.113636>
- Lichtenstein, A. H., Appel, L. J., Brands, M., Carnethon, M., Daniels, S., Franch, H. A., . . . Howard, B. (2006). Diet and lifestyle recommendations revision 2006: A scientific statement from the American Heart Association Nutrition Committee. *Circulation*, 114(1), 82-96. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.106.176158>
- Linnet, J. T. (2011). Money can't buy me hygge: Danish middle-class consumption, egalitarianism, and the sanctity of inner space. *Social Analysis*, 55(2), 21-44. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3167/sa.2011.550202>
- Livesey, G. (2011). More on mice and men: Fructose could put brakes on a vicious cycle leading to obesity in humans. *Journal of the Academy of Nutrition and Dietetics*, 111(7), 986. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jada.2011.05.020>
- Locke, K. D. (2000). *Grounded theory in management research*. London SAGE (Chapter 1).
- Lovejoy, K., Waters, R. D., & Saxton, G. D. (2012). Engaging stakeholders through Twitter: How nonprofit organizations are getting more out of 140 characters or less. *Public Relations Review*, 38(2), 313-318. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pubrev.2012.01.005>
- Lovell, J. L. (2016). How parents process child health and nutrition information: A grounded theory model. *Appetite*, 97, 138-145. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2015.11.024>
- Ludwig, D. S., Peterson, K. E., & Gortmaker, S. L. (2001). Relation between consumption of sugar-sweetened drinks and childhood obesity: a prospective, observational analysis. *The Lancet*, 357(9255), 505-508. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(00\)04041-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(00)04041-1)
- Luecking, C. T., Hennink-Kaminski, H., Ihekweazu, C., Vaughn, A., Mazzucca, S., & Ward, D. S. (2017). Social marketing approaches to nutrition and physical activity interventions in early care and education centres: a systematic review. *Obesity Reviews*, 18(12), 1425-1438. doi:10.1111/obr.12596
- Lupton, D. (2016). The use and value of digital media for information about pregnancy and early motherhood: a focus group study. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, 16(1), 171. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-016-0971-3>
- Lustig, R. H. (2013). *Sugar Has 56 Names: A Shopper's Guide (A Penguin Special from Hudson Street Press)*: Penguin.
- McDaniel, B. T., Coyne, S. M., & Holmes, E. K. (2012). New mothers and media use: Associations between blogging, social networking, and maternal well-being. *Maternal and Child Health Journal*, 16(7), 1509-1517. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10995-011-0918-2>
- Moura, A. F., & Aschemann-Witzel, J. (2020). A downturn or a window of opportunity? How Danish and French parents perceive changes in healthy eating in the transition to parenthood. *Appetite*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2020.104658>
- O'Keefe, D. (2015). *Persuasion: Theory and Research*. (3 ed.). Los Angeles SAGE.
- O'Key, V., & Hugh-Jones, S. (2010). I don't need anybody to tell me what I should be doing': A discursive analysis of maternal accounts of (mis) trust of healthy eating information. *Appetite*, 54(3), 524-532. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2010.02.007>
- Porter, N., & Ispa, J. M. (2013). Mothers' online message board questions about parenting infants and toddlers. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 69(3), 559-568. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2648.2012.06030.x>

- Moura, A. F., & Aschemann-Witzel, J. (2021). Perspectives on sugar consumption expressed on social media by French-speaking and Danish-speaking parents. *Social Science & Medicine*, 270, 113636. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2020.113636>
- Rozin, P., Fischler, C., Imada, S., Sarubin, A., & Wrzesniewski, A. (1999). Attitudes to food and the role of food in life in the USA, Japan, Flemish Belgium and France: Possible implications for the diet–health debate. *Appetite*, 33(2), 163-180.
- Rumble, J. N., Lundy, L. K., Martin, B., & Anderson, S. (2017). Gender and GMOs: Understanding Floridians attitudes toward GMOs through the lens of Social Judgment Theory. *Journal of Applied Communications*, 101(4).
- Russell, H. (2015). *The Year of Living Danishly: Uncovering the Secrets of the World's Happiest Country*. UK: Icon Books Ltd.
- Saint-Pol, T. (2015). Déterminants sociaux et culturels de l'alimentation. In Institut national de la santé et de la recherche médicale (Inserm) (Ed.), *Inégalités sociales de santé en lien avec l'alimentation et l'activité physique*. (1 ed., pp. 217-235). Paris, France: Pôle expertise collective ITMO Santé Publique, Aviesan.
- Sherif, C. W., Sherif, M., & Nebergall, R. E. (1965). *Attitude and attitude change: The social judgment-involvement approach*: Saunders Philadelphia.
- Sloan, L., & Quan-Haase, A. (2017). *The SAGE handbook of social media research methods*: SAGE
- Statista Research Department. (2019). Penetration rate of leading social networks in France during the second and third quarters of 2018. Retrieved from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/284435/social-network-penetration-france/>
- Stewart, M. C., & Arnold, C. L. (2018). Defining social listening: Recognizing an emerging dimension of listening. *International Journal of Listening*, 32(2), 85-100. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/10904018.2017.1330656>
- Sønderskov, K. M., & Dinesen, P. T. (2014). Danish exceptionalism: Explaining the unique increase in social trust over the past 30 years. *European Sociological Review*, 30(6), 782-795. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1093/esr/jcu073>
- Tebben, M. (2008). French food texts and national identity: Consommé, cheese soufflé, francité. In A. M. Magid (Ed.), *You Are What You Eat: Literary Probes into the Palate* (pp. 168-189). Newcastle: Cambridge Scholars Publishing
- The Danish Agency for Culture and Palaces. (2018). Media Development in Denmark *Summary and Discourse*. Retrieved from https://slks.dk/fileadmin/user_upload/dokumenter/medier/Mediernes_udvikling/2018/Overblik_og_perspektivering/PDF-dokumenter_Overblik_og_perspektivering/SUMMARY_AND_DISCOURSE_2018_FINAL.pdf. Accessed 09 January 2020.
- Wiking, M. (2016). *The little book of hygge: The Danish way to live well*. UK: Penguin
- Woloson, W. A. (2002). *Refined Tastes: Sugar, Confectionery, and Consumers in Nineteenth-Century America* (Vol. 120): JHU Press.
- World Health Organization. (2015a). *Guideline: Sugars intake for adults and children*. Geneva World Health Organization.
- World Health Organization. (2015b). WHO calls on countries to reduce sugars intake among adults and children: Press release. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/mediacentre/news/releases/2015/sugar-guideline/en/>. Accessed 18 December 2019.

Moura, A. F., & Aschemann-Witzel, J. (2021). Perspectives on sugar consumption expressed on social media by French-speaking and Danish-speaking parents. *Social Science & Medicine*, 270, 113636. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2020.113636>

World Health Organization. (2016). Global Strategy on Diet, Physical Activity and Health: Childhood overweight and obesity. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/dietphysicalactivity/childhood/en/>. Accessed 18 February 2020.

Appendix

Interview guide for experts:

- From your work and studies on the French/Danish population's sugar consumption, could you say something about attitudes, beliefs and practices related to sugar among French/Danish parents?
- Do you think that the beliefs about sugar among French/Danish parents differ from the beliefs of parents in other European countries? If yes, could you point out reasons for this difference?
- [Specific question for the French expert] The French food culture is well known for its emphasis on the hedonic aspects of food and eating. Do you think that “saccharophobic” messages have influenced that aspect, especially among parents? How?
- [Specific question for the Danish expert] How do you think the concept of *hygge* in the Danish culture influences the consumption of sweets by Danish families?